

From Research to Implementation: The SMAUG Pilot Use Cases in Real Port Environments

The SMAUG project enters its final phase, with only six months remaining until its completion. Since March, the project has been in its most crucial moment, the transition from development to validation and impact.

The final results of SMAUG are currently being actively tested in the project's carefully selected pilot areas. These real-world environments are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness, scalability, and practical value of the solutions developed during the SMAUG project. The testing activities will provide valuable insights to refine and enhance the final outcomes.

Meanwhile, event participation and organisation, as well as scientific publications, continue to help disseminate the research outcomes and showcase the project's contributions.

Looking ahead, several key activities have already been organised, including final demonstrations, stakeholder engagement efforts, and dissemination initiatives designed to maximise the project's impact beyond its duration.

Embark on our journey to explore SMAUG's latest news and developments!

SMAUG Pilot Tests in Greece

Elefsis Port Authority Pilot

The Elefsis pilot, conducted on 16–17 March 2026, marked the successful completion of the first Greek Use Case within the SMAUG project. The complex security environment of the Port of Elefsis, with nearby shipwrecks and mixed maritime traffic, creates ideal conditions for illicit activity. The pilot deployed all SMAUG's integrated technologies to intercept a simulated contraband operation: **hydrophones from the University of Piraeus Research Center-Quantitative Analysis in Shipping Laboratory and Universidad Politecnica De Madrid detected the acoustic signature of an approaching RHIB, triggering a**

UAV for aerial identification, a USV for hull scanning, and an ROV with multibeam sonar for underwater inspection, while ATHANOR's AIS module built a real-time maritime picture and FAVIT's platform tied it all together, locating a concealed box and enabling the Hellenic Coast Guard to investigate the threat. Despite challenging weather conditions, all partners worked continuously, with special recognition going to the Elefsis Port Authority and UPRC for their outstanding organisation and hosting.

Discover the Elefsis Pilot

Heraklion Port Authority Pilot

The Heraklion pilot, the second and final Greek Use Case, was conducted at one of Greece's busiest passenger and commercial ports, where the Heraklion Port Authority granted full access to critical infrastructure for real-world testing. As in Elefsis, the port faces underwater security vulnerabilities that conventional surveillance cannot address and the SMAUG system responded with the same layered approach: **hydrophones from University of Piraeus Research Center-Quantitative Analysis in Shipping Laboratory and the Universidad Politecnica De Madrid** continuously monitored the underwater environment, triggering a **UAV dispatch upon anomaly detection**, while **ATHANOR's AIS module correlated vessel identities and trajectories in real time**, and an **ROV conducted detailed underwater inspection to identify concealed objects beyond the reach of standard surveillance**. When suspicious activity was confirmed, real-time alerts enabled the Hellenic Coast Guard to intervene immediately.

Discover the Heraklion Pilot

With Heraklion's successful conclusion, all SMAUG Greek Use Cases are now complete, and the project will now continue its pilot tests in Norway and Valencia.

Port of Call: Latest News & Events

The SMAUG project has been actively showcasing its innovative research and work at key industry and academic events across Europe. From **major industry events to pilot testings and General Assembly meetings**, explore the latest highlights and reflections from SMAUG's event participation.

SMAUG at the Borderless Border Management

The SMAUG project participated in the **Borderless Border Management 2026** event held in Narva, Estonia.

[Read more](#)

SMAUG 4th General Assembly Meeting

From 22nd to 23rd October, the SMAUG consortium partners gathered for the project's 4th General Assembly Meeting at the historic Piraeus Chamber of Commerce and Industry, one of Greece's oldest and most esteemed chambers.

[Read more](#)

SMAUG Pilot Magazine

The SMAUG project will showcase and validate the multiple solutions developed during the project in real port environments. Our partners are sharing the collective insights and updates on the technical validations conducted before the actual pilot

testing.

Click to explore each issue!

SMAUG Publications

The SMAUG publications cover research findings, technical developments, and operational use cases that support the protection of ports, vessels, and critical maritime infrastructure and more!

Explore all the SMAUG
publications

What's next?

With the Greek Pilot Use Case successfully completed, SMAUG now moves to its next pilots in **Norway and Valencia**, where the system will be tested in new operational environments. Joint webinars will be announced in the coming weeks, as well as further project activities and events just before the project's completion in September!

Stay tuned and join the SMAUG journey by following its social media profiles!

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